

APPLICATION OF EFFECTIVE MEDIUM THEORY TO CNF-IMPREGNATED POLYESTER-BASED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

We demonstrate here the use of a modified version of standard effective medium theory to model both electrical and thermal conductivity in nanocomposites below the percolation threshold. The model has been used to explain our measurements in carbon nanofiber-based bulk nanocomposites and other thin film nanostructures.

Keywords: Modelling; Effective Medium Theory; Hopping; Composites; Carbon Nanofibers.

INTRODUCTION

Effective medium theory (EMT), more specifically the Maxwell-Garnett and Bruggeman-Landauer (B-L) forms, has been widely used to describe various physical properties of composite media. We have applied modified versions of both of these models towards an understanding of the thermal and electrical properties of an extended set of polyester-based bulk nanocomposites (NC) containing small volume percentages of carbon nanofibers (CNFs), the latter being added with a view to enhancing the above-mentioned transport properties. In-house thermal conductivity measurements made on these nanocomposites have proved to be very challenging but, at the same time, the data have proved to be relatively easy to model in terms of CNF content, using EMT. The most useful aspect of the model, perhaps, as far as thermal measurements are concerned, is its ability to determine an effective depolarization factor for the nanofibers.

Electrical conductivity is a relatively straightforward parameter to measure in these nanocomposites, other than in the case of very low CNF content. It is, however, comparatively difficult to model. One problem here lies in the extremely low percolation threshold for electrical conduction in even random assemblies of highly acicular nanostructures. Below percolation, we have adapted the EMT to account for the electrical conductivity of the matrix in terms of thermally assisted hopping. Using this approach, we have been able to use basically the same EMT formulation to describe both electrical and thermal conductivity, even though, in the latter case, there is no evidence of thermal percolation.

MODEL

In nanocomposites, the low-field conductivity can be shown to be dominated by thermally-activated hopping of the carriers and, in an isotropic system with spherical nanoparticles, has been widely shown to be of the form $\sigma_L = \sigma_0 \exp\left[-2\left(\frac{C}{kT}\right)^{1/2}\right]$

(1)

Since the hopping between grains determines the matrix conductivity, then the latter, in our EMT equations, can be replaced by Eq.(1).

RESULTS

EMT is used in modeling the electrical conductivity and thermal conductivity of the nanocomposites. The modeled results are also compared with the experimental data. Good agreement can be observed in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1. The electrical conductivity varies with the CNF weight fraction. (- model; * experimental data)

Figure 2. The thermal conductivity varies with the CNF weight fraction. (- model; * experimental data)

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